

Ethovision: Elevated Plus Maze

- New → create name of file → Ok
- Experiment Settings → Tracked Features → center, nose, and tail base detection

Arena Settings

- Arena Settings → Arena Settings 1 → Grab Image/Browse → Find video → Grab at start of video
- Click 1. Draw Scale to Calibrate: 65cm from top to bottom
- Click 2. Select Shape and Draw Arena → click closed polyline tool → click points outside maze to trace the arena (to avoid interference from glare on floor)
- Click 3. Select Shape and Draw Zones → under Zone Group 1 → create closed polyline for each section and label: Closed Arm 1, Closed Arm 2, Open Arm 1, Open Arm 2, Center
- Add Cumulative Zone “OPEN” → drag over open arm zones → Ok
 - The cumulative zone icon is the 3rd from the right underneath the zones list
- Add Cumulative Zone “CLOSED” → drag over closed arm zones → Ok
- Optional: draw zones “Edges 1” and “Edges 2” outside the open arms and create cumulative zone “EDGES”
- Click 4. Validate Setup
- Rename Arena Settings 1 to the animal ID#

Trial Control Settings

- Trial Control Settings 1 → delete first green box → check box next to Time
- In the time condition box → Settings → change condition name to “Start” → select After and enter the number of seconds when the mouse first appears in the video and the experimenter is also out of view
 - Make sure there are 5 minutes of video after the mouse’s start time
- Connect all boxes in timeline with arrows; the “Start” time condition box should be in the second position
- In the second time condition box → Settings → change condition name to “Stop” → set delay of 5 minutes
- Rename Trial Control Settings 1 to animal ID#

Detection Settings

- Detection Settings 1 → Automated Setup → select Rodent → pause when mouse is elongated and draw box from base of tail to tip of nose → make sure it's tracking → Yes
 - Glance at Detection Performance → Missed samples/Interpolated samples/Subject not found to confirm tracking
- Rename Detection Settings 1 to animal ID# → click Save to save file

The screenshot shows the 'Detection Settings' window. It includes a video feed of a rodent in an arena, a playback control bar with a progress slider and play/pause buttons, and a 'Detection Performance' section with a table.

Arena	Subject	Missed samples	Subject not found
Arena 1	Subject 1	0.0% (0 samples)	0.0% (0 samples)

Repeat for all animals

- Duplicate each previous Arena, Trial, and Detection
- Rename each to the next animal ID and adjust for next video
- For all new videos, only reorient the original arena, do not resize or move individual pieces—you can click and drag across the whole set-up to select it all, and then drag/rotate the entire thing
- If there is a note that the camera zoom changed between recordings, then redo the arena set-up for the video in which it changed, and reuse that set-up thereafter

Trial List

- Trial List → Add Trials → # of Animals → Ok
- Add Variable → rename animal ID#
- Add Videos → Alphabetical → Browse → select all videos and import them in order from same folder

- Make list in numerical order of animal ID#s → copy and paste into blank columns →
 - Each row should have the same animal ID#s all across

Acquisition

- Acquisition → Acquisition → Track All Planned → Ready for Start (red circle button)
- Videos are analyzed
- Track editor → if using 3 body points, then check if trials need arrow swaps; refer to arrow swap protocol

Analysis

- Results → Heatmap visualization → plot heatmaps
- Double check for any abnormal video analyses
- If you want to check how behaviors are registering as they happen, see Integrated Visualization

Example of Normal Heatmap:

- Analysis Profile 1 → Location → In Zone
- Within that box, under the In Zone tab → deselect Arena → select Center, Cumulative Zone OPEN, and Cumulative Zone CLOSED (drop-down → For each selected zone)
- On the body point tab → Center-point (drop-down → All selected points)
- Under Trial Statistics → only select Frequency + Cumulative Duration
- Optional: add another In Zone box → deselect Arena → select Cumulative Zone EDGES + Nose-point → Trial Statistics → only select Frequency + Cumulative Duration → Add
- Under the Statistics and Charts section, make sure the top says Data Profile 1 + Analysis Profile 1 → Calculate → once done click Export Data and save file

To add Peeking Behavior:

- Data profile 1 → Duplicate + Rename “Peeking”
- In Zone → select only Center (drop-down → When in any of the selected zones) → Center-point (drop-down → All selected points) → OK → add to middle of timeline and connect arrows
- Duplicate Analysis Profile 1 → rename “Peeking” → delete previous In Zone line/variable
- Add In Zone → select only Cumulative Zone OPEN (drop-down → Each selected zone) → Nose-point (drop-down → All selected points) → Add
- Statistics and Charts → make sure Peeking + Peeking are at top
- Calculate → once done click Export Data and save file